

***Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n. (Neuroptera: Myrmeleontidae)
from Sichuan, China**

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ABSTRACT. *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n. (Neuroptera: Myrmeleontidae) from Sichuan, China.

Myrmeleon wangxinlii sp. n. is described from China and compared with other Asian *Myrmeleon* species: *Myrmeleon formicarius* LINNAEUS, 1767, *Myrmeleon trivialis* GERSTAECKER, 1885, *Myrmeleon oberthuri* NAVÁS, 1923, *Myrmeleon ferrugineipennis* BAO, 2009. *Myrmeleon montanus* NAVÁS, 1914 (syn. n.) from India and *Myrmeleon wangi* MILLER et STANGE, 1999 (syn. n.) from Taiwan are new synonyms of *Myrmeleon trivialis* GERSTAECKER, 1885. Eight figures are appended.

KEY WORDS: new species, ant-lion, Myrmeleontidae, Sichuan, China.

INTRODUCTION

China is a huge country, stretching from the taiga belt of the northern temperate zone to the subtropical monsoon rain forests of the northern hemisphere. In this territory, very dry deserts, high mountains, high plateaus and basins can be found. Owing to its large area and diversity of natural conditions, the country has a remarkably rich and diverse fauna. Many species of ant-lions live in this diverse natural area but this fauna has not yet been satisfactorily studied.

Many Chinese ant-lion tribes and genera have recently been completely revised, for example: *Acanthaclisini* (BAO *et al.* 2004), *Bullanga* (ZHAN & WANG 2014), *Dendroleon* (WAN *et al.* 2004), *Deutoleon* (ZHAN *et al.* 2012a), *Epacanthaclisis* (AO *et al.* 2010), *Euroleon* (AO *et al.* 2009), *Gatzara* (WANG *et al.* 2012), *Hagenomyia* (BAO *et al.* 2007), *Layahima* (WAN *et al.* 2006) and *Myrmeleon* (BAO *et al.* 2006, 2009) etc., but these studies require further revision (ZHAN *et al.* 2011, 2012b).

Many ant-lion species from China and SE Asia have been described in the 20th and the 21st centuries. Even so, there is still no checklist of the Chinese ant-lion, listing valid names and synonyms.

A comprehensive revision of the genus *Myrmeleon* was carried out by Chinese researchers (BAO *et al.* 2006, 2009), which included a recently described species from Taiwan (MILLER *et al.* 1999).

We intend to continue the necessary revisions of SE Asian ant-lions. In parallel, more and more species are being recorded in this area, thereby enriching the Chinese fauna (AO *et al.* 2009, ZHAN *et al.* 2012b, ÁBRAHÁM 2016).

In this paper we describe a new *Myrmeleon* species collected during an occasional collecting trip.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Habitus photos were taken with a Canon EOS 400 digital camera equipped with a flash light system (Sigma EM140 DM). Other photos were taken using SZX9 Olympus stereomicroscope equipped with a ScopeTek DCM 800 digital camera. The layers of photos were processed with Combine ZP imagine stacking and Adobe Photoshop software.

The genital organs specified in the relevant literature were dissected. The caudal part of the abdomen was removed, treated with 10% KOH and heated for 15 minutes. After cooling, it was rinsed in distilled water. Finally, the genitalia were transferred to glycerine in a microvial for further examination and preservation.

RESULTS

***Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n.** (Figs. 1–8)

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Material examined:

Holotype male: CHINA, Sichuan, 15 km North of Maoxian H-1600m N29°19.557' E099°04.693', 28.08.2014, leg. Floriani & Saldaitis.

Paratypes: 2 females as holotype, 1 female CHINA, N. Sichuan, 20 km N Maoxian H-1120m N29°19.557' E099°04.693', 30.07.2016, leg. Floriani & Saldaitis.

The holotype and 2 paratypes are deposited in the entomological collection of the Rippl-Rónai Museum, Kaposvár (Hungary); 1 female paratype is deposited in the entomological collection of the Upper Silesian Museum, Bytom (Poland).

Fig. 1. Habitus of the holotype of *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n. (scale in mm) (photo L. Ábrahám).

Ryc. 1. Postać dorosła *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n., holotyp (skala w mm) (fot. L. Ábrahám).

Description. *Head:* Vertex strongly arched in the frontal view, entirely dull black, hairless. Frons and gena glossy black, hairless. Anterior part of clypeus glossy brown, basal part yellow. Labrum yellow, basal margin concave centrally with short sparse ochre hairs. Base of mandible predominantly yellow, brown to black apically. Maxillary and labial palps yellow. Last segment of labial palp spindle-shaped with round and yellow sensory pit. Eye large and glossy brown. Antenna about 7.5 mm long. Scape glossy black basally and yellow anteriorly. Pedicel predominantly yellow with glossy black basal spot. Majority of flagellar segments dark brown the middle ones indistinctly yellow on the outside. Flagellar segments covered by short brown setae.

Thorax: Pronotum slightly wider than long, with a narrow yellow strip on anterior margin extending towards lateral margin (Fig. 2). Short sparse black hairs on pronotum. Meso- and metanotum almost entirely dark brown. Meso- and metascutellum with indistinct small oval-shaped yellow spots on each side. Caudal parts of meso- and metascutum with narrow yellow edge. Meso- and metanotum with very short sparse and pale hairs. Side completely dark brown with very short sparse black and pale hairs (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Pronotum in dorsal view of *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n. (photo L. Ábrahám).

Ryc. 2. Przedplecze *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n., widok z góry (fot. L. Ábrahám).

Legs: Fore leg, coxa brown with sparse silky and pale hairs. Femur almost wholly yellow but distal end and inner side brown, covered with short, smooth, black hairs and long, stiff, erect black bristles. Both ends and outer side of tibia dark brown with sparse black hairs and long stiff erect black bristles. Tibial spurs as long as tarsal segments 1-2 combined. Femur somewhat longer than tibia. Tarsal segments yellow, only distal part of segment 5 brown, segment 1 longer than segment 2. Segments 2-4 equal. Tarsal segment 5 somewhat shorter than segments 1-4 combined. Claws about as long as tibial spurs. Color and chaetotaxy of mid leg similar to fore leg but with many long stiff erect black

Fig. 3. Side and legs in lateral view of *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n. (photo L. Ábrahám).
Ryc. 3. Bok i nogi *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n., widok z boku (fot. L. Ábrahám).

Fig. 4. Fore and hind wings of *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n. C – Costa, Sc – Subcosta, Rs – Radius sector, PBI – Posterior Banksian-line (photo L. Ábrahám).
Ryc. 4. Przednie i tylne skrzydła *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n. C – żyłka ramieniowa, Sc – żyłka podramieniowa, Rs – żyłka sektoralna, PBI – tylna linia Banksa (fot. L. Ábrahám).

Fig. 5. Male genitalia in lateral view of *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n. (by Á. Nagy).

Ryc. 5. Genitalia samca *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n., widok z boku (rys. Á. Nagy).

Fig. 6. Shape of sternite 8 in ventral view of *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n. (by Á. Nagy).

Ryc. 6. Kształt ósmego sternitu *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n., widok od strony brzusznej (rys. Á. Nagy).

bristles on femur and tibia more than on fore leg. Femur as long as tibia, tibial spurs somewhat shorter than tarsal segments 1-2 combined. Hind leg femur somewhat longer than tibia, tibial spurs somewhat longer than tarsal segment 1.

Wings: Fore wing: 42 mm long, 11 mm wide. Hind wing: 39 mm long, 10 mm wide. Apices subacute, anal area obtuse. Membrane transparent, indistinct light brown shadow at cross veins in cubital area. Venation dense. C yellow, Sc yellow and basal part also yellow and interrupted with brown at intersections of cross-veins. Pattern on other longitudinal veins similar to Sc but cross-veins predominantly yellow on distal part of wing. 8-10 radial cross-veins before origin of Rs. 10-11 branches in Rs. Posterior Banksian-line visible. Pterostigma indistinct, yellowish white with 6-7 cross-veins (Fig. 4).

Hind wing pattern similar to that of fore wing. Pterostigma small, indistinct, yellowish white with 4 cross-veins. 5 radial cross-veins before origin of Rs. Rs with 10-11 branches. Pilula axillaris present, small, rounded with sparse long and yellowish red setae.

Abdomen: 30-31 mm long, dark brown with indistinct small yellow pattern at both ends of segments in lateral view. Pubescence short, dense, erect and black.

Genitalia: Male. In lateral view, tergite 9 subrhomboid in shape, dark brown with yellow hind margin. Ectoproct subtriangular-shaped yellow with moderately long black hairs on distal margins. Ventral edge of ectoproct slightly concave without disto-caudal processus, only with long black hairs curved distally (Fig. 5). Shape of sternite 8 as in Fig. 6, brown with long black hairs on margins in ventral view. Gonarcus-parameres complex in caudal view as in Fig. 7.

Female. Female genitalia in lateral view as in Fig. 8.

Etymology: The new species is dedicated to Prof. Dr. Wang Xinli, Department of Entomology, China Agricultural University, (Beijing, China) who made a significant contribution to the neuropteran fauna of China.

Fig. 7. Gonarcus-parameres complex in caudal view of *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n. (by Á. Nagy).

Ryc. 7. Kompleks gonobazy i paramer *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n., widok od tyłu (rys. Á. Nagy).

Fig. 8. Female genitalia in lateral view of *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n. (by Á. Nagy).

Ryc. 8. Genitalia samicy *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n., widok z boku (rys. Á. Nagy).

Diagnosis: The genus *Myrmeleon* is rich in species (STANGE 2004). Many of which inhabit the Palaearctic and Oriental regions. The new species belongs to the large *Myrmeleon* species, which have a 35 mm long fore wing. Three species from this genus (*Myrmeleon formicarius* LINNAEUS, 1767, *Myrmeleon ferrugineipennis* BAO, 2009, *Myrmeleon trivialis* GERSTAECKER, 1885) are known in China and one species (*Myrmeleon wangi* MILLER et STANGE, 1999) in Taiwan. *Myrmeleon formicarius* LINNAEUS, 1767 is widespread in the Palaearctic but only known from NE China, Japan, Korea, and the Russian Far East (KRIVOKHATSKY 1998). The species is easily distinguished by the absence of the pilula axillaris, while *M. wangxinlii* sp. nov., as well as *Myrmeleon ferrugineipennis* BAO, 2009 and *M. trivialis* GERSTAECKER, 1885 have this organ.

The apical part of the hind wing of *M. ferrugineipennis* BAO, 2009 is falcate, the longitudinal veins are mainly monochrome, the trochanters are yellow in the lateral view and the ectoproct has a small ventro-caudal pointed process. In the new species, the hind wings are not concave right under the apices the longitudinal veins are yellow, interrupted with dark brown stripes at the intersection with the cross-veins, the trochanters are dark brown on the side and the ventro-caudal part of the ectoproct is rounded.

The wings of *M. trivialis* GERSTAECKER, 1885 are narrow and their apices are pointed. In contrast, the wings of *M. wangxinlii* sp. n. are broad, so their tips seem to be rather rounded. In the Oriental region *M. trivialis* GERSTAECKER, 1885 is widely distributed and it is morphologically variable, so several new synonyms are proposed: *M. montanus* NAVÁS, 1914 syn. n. from India, *M. wangi* MILLER et STANGE, 1999 syn. n. from Taiwan are new synonyms of *M. GERSTAECKER*, 1885.

Based on NAVÁS's description (1923) *M. oberthuri* (NAVÁS, 1923), under the original combination of *Talosos oberthuri* NAVÁS, 1923, a monotypic species from East India (GHOSH 1984) – is also very similar to *M. trivialis*, and may be conspecific with it, but neither type specimens, nor appropriate illustrations of this species are available to clarify its taxonomic status. Based on the original description, *M. wangxinlii* sp. n. differs from it in its measurement and pronotal pattern, in the number of fore wing radial veins and the pattern of the legs.

The type specimen of *Myrmeleon mediatius* (NAVÁS, 1931) once preserved in Hamburg, was destroyed in the Second World War. Based on the pronotal pattern and measurements (NAVÁS 1931), it differs from the new species, but appears rather similar to *Myrmeleon trivialis* and may be conspecific with the latter.

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STRESZCZENIE

Myrmeleon wangxinlii sp. n. (Neuroptera: Myrmeleontidae) z Syczuanu, Chiny

Publikacja zawiera opis nowego dla nauki gatunku mrówkolwa *Myrmeleon wangxinlii* sp. n., z prowincji Syczuan w Chinach. Autor, poza obszernym opisem, ilustrowanym rysunkami i fotografiami dokumentującymi cechy taksonomiczne, porównuje go z innymi wykazywanymi z Azji przedstawicielami rodzaju *Myrmeleon*: *M. formicarius* LINNAEUS, 1767, *M. trivialis* GERSTAECKER, 1885, *M. oberthuri* NAVÁS, 1923, *M. ferrugineipennis* BAO, 2009. *Myrmeleon montanus* NAVÁS, 1914 oraz *M. wangi* MILLER et STANGE, 1999 uznane zostały za synonimy *M. trivialis*.

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